

THE BIOGRAPHY OF A SYMBOL: AN INTRODUCTION TO HASHTAGS IN SOCIAL MEDIA DISCOURSE QASIM OBAYES AL-AZZAWI, HANEEN ALI HALEEM

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ABSTRACT

Throughout the last two decades, the number of linguistic studies on online discourse has increased gradually. The rapid development in technology and its effect on the language used in digitally mediated communication both lead to the creation of new linguistic conventions, one of which is the hashtag. Despite the numerous works conducted on hashtags in interdisciplinary fields such as information technology and marketing, only few studies devoted to the hashtag tend to stress its function as a linguistic element. Therefore, this study aims to present a comprehensive overview of the works that analyse the hashtag on different linguistic levels, ranging from the morpho-syntactical to the socio-pragmatic level. The review is preceded by an introduction to the concept of the hashtag in cyber language, describing its development towards an essential feature of the language used on social media platforms. A comparison is drawn between the results obtained in previous works, and a number of aspects are pointed out to be examined in future research.

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1. Introduction

The rapid development in technology and its effect on the language used in digitally mediated communication both lead to the creation of new linguistic conventions, one of which is the hashtag. According to the Twitter website, a hashtag can be defined as characters preceded by the symbol # (hash, or pound), as in #linguistics. It has no case sensitivity, so that #LANGUAGE, #language, or any alternative combination of upper and lower case is possible, and would be identified as the same unit. Instead, no white spaces are allowed. Hashtags that include two or more (recognizable) words could be clarified by capitalizing the initial letter of each word, as in #CyberLanguage instead of #cyberlanguage. Hashtags may contain numbers but could not be made up of numerical digits only (e.g. #123), nor start with a number (e.g. #123abc). No special characters are allowed either (e.g. !, %, *, \$ etc.), with the exception of the underscore (_) (Caleffi, 2015).

Being a relatively recent invention in online discourse, it is necessary to analyse and classify the different functions that the hashtag performs on social media platforms. The present paper starts off by describing the environment in which the hashtag appeared, the cyber space, after which a discussion moved on to the linguistic functions of hashtags. Finally, a number of related works are discussed, which involve several attempts to analyse the functionality of hashtags online.

2. SOCIAL MEDIA AND CYBER LANGUAGE

Social networking has always been a distinct feature of human communication and an integral part of their everyday life. The recent technological developments such as the emergence of mobile smartphones and the spread of (Wi-Fi) internet had a fundamental role in 'digitalizing' this act of social networking. After the invention of cyberspace, better known as commercial internet, the concept of sharing information online evolved noticeably, as both the service itself and the user's approach to it have developed over time. It is therefore necessary to distinguish between two different eras of internet use, namely Web 1.0 and Web 2.0 (O'Reilly, 2009).

The initial form of internet during the 90's used to be a rather informational network. It consisted of static pages with content that was created by web-designers only. The main aim was to share information that users could only read, without making a contribution of any kind to the content presented. At the turn of the century, a major shift was noticed towards the internet as an interpersonal resource, marking the birth of the Social Web, or Web 2.0. This new form of internet is used to enact relationships rather than simply share information, with the web users being creators and self-publishers of (multimedia) content, rather than just consumers (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2009). Hsu and Park (2011) drew a general comparison between the characteristics of these two eras, as presented in Table 1.

Table 1. A general comparison between Web 1.0 and Web 2.0 (Hsu & Park, 2011).

Features	Web 1.0	Web 2.0
Mode of use	Read	Write and contribute
Unit of content	Page	Record
State	Static	Dynamic
How content is viewed	Web browser	Browsers, RSS readers, mobile devices, etc.
Creation of content	By website authors	By everyone
Domain of	Web designers	A new culture of public research

This comparison shows that the development of such a virtual internet-based environment, the social media, enabled individuals to interact and cooperate without being restricted by temporal or spatial factors.

When analysing Web 2.0 or the Social Web, a clear distinction needs to be made in terms of the participant's purpose for using the internet to communicate, being it to exchange actions or objects (often referred to as 'goods and services'), or to seek and receive information (Halliday M. , Introduction to Functional Grammar, 1994). From this perspective, social media interactions are oriented towards the exchange of information and tends to emphasize interpersonal exchange rather than task-based transactions. They thus differ from sites where the primary purpose is to allow a customer to purchase goods (e.g. online stores, making hotel reservations, buying tickets for a journey) (Page, Barton, Unger, & Zappavigna, 2014). Common examples of social media are discussing forums and social networking sites (e.g. Facebook, Twitter), as well as content-sharing platforms (YouTube, TikTok).

Research into microblogging is a multidisciplinary field extending to domains outside linguistics, such as psychology, media studies, marketing, opinion mining, machine learning, and many others. It often focuses on snapshots of real-time microblogging communication at particular temporal or contextual moments. Given the diverse and extensive range of naturally occurring discourse on Twitter, significant work has been conducted on this platform across most major fields in linguistics, ranging from pragmatics, sociolinguistics, corpus linguistics to computational linguistics (Zappavigna, 2017).

Throughout the last two decades, general studies of online discourse from a linguistic perspective are gradually becoming well-established (Crystal, 2006; Baron 2008). However, determining whether the analysis of linguistic function and structure could provide a definition of online communities remains an area of inquiry. Approaches to affiliation within sociolinguistics and discourse analysis have used concepts such as speech communities (Labov, 1973) to explore linguistic patterning and social structure (Zappavigna, 2012). Such a concept was introduced in Rheingold's (2000) work on virtual communities, where he stated that the latter are social aggregations which emerge from the Net whenever a sufficient number of people carry on certain public discussions for a long enough time, in order to form networks of personal relations within cyber-space (Rheingold, 2000).

Some language-based research on social media communities was established by computational linguists within the area of sentiment analysis – and Natural Language Processing (NLP). A number of works attempted on the automatization of detecting language patterns so as to categorize groups of users into social networks (AL-Qurishi, et al., 2015). Another study grouped communities purely based on their sentiment, using mood tags (metadata applied to blogpost by authors) and 'emotion-bearing words' extracted from the content of posts (Kieu & Pham, 2010).

3. THE BIOGRAPHY OF A SYMBOL

It is generally believed that the history of the hashtag (as it is known today), began with a tweet by the internet activist Chris Messina in 2007, where he suggested the use of the # sign to indicate groups of topics on Twitter. On his blog Factory Joe, he clarified that it would be useful to improve contextualizing, content filtering, and exploratory serendipity on Twitter" (Messina, 2007). As two other hashtag theorists have underscored, the symbol was initially meant to function as a "coordinating mechanism" (Bruns & Burgess, 2015). Today, Messina is referred to as the "inventor of the hashtag" (Bernard, 2019).

During the summer of 2007, one year after Twitter's launch, various internet activists and the company itself were occupied with the question of how to organize the ever growing and unstructured mass of tweets. The # symbol had, in fact, already had a long history in the organization of online communication. In his blog entry, Messina referred to Internet Relay Chat (IRC), an early text-based online platform whose communicative channels were based on hash signs and key words. He thought that it might be a good idea to transfer this existing classification system to the new format of microblogging (Bernard, 2019).

The typographical element first began to receive greater attention in October 2007, when devastating forest fires broke out in San Diego. Images of the fires were posted on social media platforms, and Messina urged people on his blog to use this in their tweets as a "hashtag", as he started to call it. More and more users followed this suggestion and by the end of October, the hashtag #sandiegofire was spreading like the fires themselves (Bernard, 2019).

By the end of 2007 enough people had started use the hashtag, which lead Twitter to decide to embrace it (Pandell, 2017). As of April, 2009 every profile page showed a list of 'trending topics', and soon this became synonymous with a list of the most frequently used hashtags. A few weeks later, the company finally introduced a function that automatically linked hashtags and allowed users to view all the tweets related to a given hashtag by clicking on one, thus forming a hyperlink.

In 2013, the American Dialect Society elected the "hashtag" to be the "word of the year", and in 2014 it was accepted in the Oxford English Dictionary. In an interview conducted on the tenth anniversary of his historic tweet, Chris Messina claimed that in digital culture, the hashtag has become the "lingua franca for labeling content" (Pandell, 2017). Since a symbol (#) is used, rather than an abbreviation, the act of hashtagging seems to be used similarly in different languages. These types of linguistic conventions occur in a number of languages used on social media, thereby creating some sort of a dialectic comprehension among users along the lines of lingua franca (Iaia, 2016).

4. LINGUISTIC FUNCTIONS OF HASHTAGS

The few linguistic studies devoted to the hashtag tend to stress its categorial function as a linguistic element. In their current usage, according to Paola-Maria Caleffi, hashtags are "linguistic items whose character does not match any part of speech in the traditional sense of the term". As it oscillates between text and metadata, and signifying and networking, hashtags are "both words and not yet words" (Caleffi, 2015). As the hashtag was initially invented to label and categorize posts on social media platforms, this linguistic invention tends to function as a keyword for the content of these posts. To create a wider comprehension of this concept, it would be useful to go back to the defining features of keywords, as referred to in library sciences.

According to Heinrich Roloff (1973), the keyword is the shortest factually relevant expression for the topic represented in an individual book. Agnes Stählin added that the purpose of the keyword is to generate correct ideas in the user about the content of particular books (Stählin, 1950). On the other hand, another discipline where key words have a primarily function is historical linguistics.

Wilhelm Bauer (1920) wrote an article about the keyword as a social and psychological phenomenon of intellectual history. He stated that when a word transforms into a keyword, it distances itself from its original conceptual basis. They are thus transferred from their factual and logical stage into a phase that is emotional (Bauer, 1920). "Emotionality" would in fact become one of the defining criteria in the methodology of historical keyword research (Bernard, 2019). In an extensive study, Wülfing (1982) identified six features of epoch-defining keywords: abbreviation, emotionalizing, anti-rationality, indeterminable content, apparent clarity, and the compulsion to repeat them (Wülfing, 1982).

In light of the studies discussed above, this constant focus on the "emotionality" is interesting in two respects. First, the meaning of the keyword in historical linguistics is exactly the opposite of its meaning in library sciences. In the latter, the keyword has served an organizational and categorial function and has thus stood for a principle of rationality. The "emotional content" of the keywords which has been a central feature of its linguistic application since Bauer's time, has not role at all when it comes to organizing inventories of knowledge.

Second, this concentration on the "emotional charge" of keywords is especially noteworthy in relation to the hashtag, as there is a particular significance of "emotionality" today in the practice of keywords on social media. Effective hashtags may arouse feelings of empathy, solidarity, or identification (as with the hashtag #BlackLivesMatter which fights racism, or #MeToo that supported the sense of sisterhood between women who were subjected to forms of harassment), thus fulfilling the emotional criteria. Bauer stated that it is the emotional aspect which turns a word into a keyword, and this aspect particularly cannot be determined intellectually. "In the end, it can only be felt" (Bauer, 1920).

The hashtag thus has two forebears in the history of knowledge in the 20th century: the keyword as a unit for organizing documents, and as a characteristic expression of a historical epoch or political agenda. The first branch of its heritage is indicative of its taxonomic function, while the second branch points to its

semantic function. In the hashtag, one could see that these two branches have been brought together. On the one hand, it serves to classify social media posts (just like a library catalog), whereas on the other hand, this act of classification is no longer performed by a committee of librarians but it is rather something that can be done by anyone on social networks. Hashtags became thus, as Gene Smith (2008) noted, "user-defined labels to organize and share information" and "people-powered metadata". Since 2004, one term has been used to designate this freely accessible form of classifying inventories of knowledge, namely the neologism folksonomy, which is a coinage combining the words "folk" and "taxonomy". Thomas Vander Wal, who claims to have invented the term, has stressed on his blog that in the sphere of social tagging, producers and consumers are one and the same, with respect to assigning keywords, a "folksonomy" knows no external authority (Vander Wal, 2007).

Despite the fact that hashtags were originally introduced so as to tag and organize tweets, thereby making it easier to have and follow discussions on particular topics online, yet the widespread use has been accompanied with a boost of creativity and variation in terms of their deployment. The following studies explore the different (linguistic) functions of hashtags on social media platforms that have been developed lately.

5. RELATED ANALYSES OF HASHTAG FUNCTIONS

A number of scholars have attempted to analyse the morphological and syntactic features of hashtags, including their structure as well as their position within posts.

Caleffi (2015) examined hashtagging as a new morphological process for word formation by looking at a corpus of English and Italian hashtags both online and offline. She proposed a tentative taxonomy of eight types of English hashtags (see Table 2.4). In her study, she explored the nature of these new linguistic items and their composition. She describes hashtagging as a new productive word formation mechanism that can be utilized to generate innovative linguistic items by stringing several words together, in a sense that may even lead to the redefinition of traditional word and part of speech categories. In her model, Caleffi's (2015) takes into account the number of words in the hashtag and its position within the post, whether at the beginning, middle or end. The items that follow the "#" symbol are also analyzed, whether these include acronyms, combinations of digits and letters, symbols, or words and phrases.

Maity et al. (2015) describe hashtags as "one of the most important linguistic units of social media", and pointed out that it is thus worthwhile to analyze them from a linguistic perspective. They performed a quantitative analysis of the evolution of the basic linguistic features of hashtags over a two-year period. The researchers found that several hashtags have 'coalesced' or combined to form new ones over a short period of time, which have come to be known as 'Twitter idioms'. They also observed that the frequency of occurrence of this new merged hashtag is usually much higher than that of its individual components. According to Maity et al. (2015), "what started as a way for people to connect with others through organizing tweets, propagating ideas, and promoting specific people or topics has now grown into a language of its own". Their findings also revealed that people tend to repeat the same hashtag in their tweets to express strong opinions or overexcitement.

Lin (2017), on the other hand, maintains that "hashtags stimulate people to build their own language", thereby suggesting the concept of the hashtag as a paralanguage. They are very easy to produce since anyone can create a new hashtag just by adding the pound symbol "#" before a word or phrase, which makes them uncontrollable but creative. The presence of hashtags thus encourages people to use slang expressions or even create their own merged forms that then circulate on a large scale and start infiltrating into everyday language. Although they may not be syntactically formal or lack grammaticality, "such a form of Internet slang evolved into mainstream language" (Lin, 2017). He also found that the coalescing phenomenon is more common in social media than in standard written language due to informality and space limitation.

Apart from their primary categorizing and searching functionalities, hashtags have developed to serve a range of linguistic and pragmatic functions that have constituted the focus of several studies.

In her pioneering article, Zappavigna (2011) tackled the role performed by hashtags as technologically discursive tools. She described hashtags as 'searchable talk' since they promote "searchability" as a community-building linguistic activity. By using a hashtag, it is assumed that other users will adopt the same tag, hence creating what is known as a 'folksonomy' or a virtual community that engages in collaborative tagging. She defined the concept of 'searchable talk' as online conversation where people actively render their talk more findable (Zappavigna, 2011). In a later work, she attempted to identify the pragmatic functions of hashtags, distinguishing between enacting experience, negotiating relationships, and organizing information (Zappavigna, 2015).

Tamara (2011) presents a classification of hashtag functions into informing and commentary hashtags (opinions/ judgments), and stated that about 71% of tweets on Twitter involved informing hashtags. Zimmer (2011), on the other hand, devoted special attention to the use of hashtags for irony, particularly as a "vehicle for self-directed sarcasm". Furthermore, Zimmer (2011) recommended that these sarcastic hashtags, especially those involving race- and class-based self-mocking, should be examined more thoroughly "to make way for a deeper self-examination" (Zimmer, 2011).

Page (2012) classified hashtags into three categories based on the clause/content type surrounding the hashtag in use: declarative, imperative, and question. She also found that celebrities use hashtags for self-branding. They do this through two main types of posts: those related to professional identity and those related to national events, such that "search terms related to professional expertise tend to emphasize the tweet author's identity as a practitioner within a particular field". She suggests that celebrities employ hashtags as a sort of marketing strategy through which they persuade their audience to watch a show or purchase a product to promote their status in the offline world.

Wikström (2014) employed the Speech Act Theory to analyse the communicative functions of hashtags and distinguished eight functions, including playing games and providing parenthetical explanations, in addition to emotive, emphatic, and humorous usages. Shapp (2014), on the other hand, explored the variation in sociolinguistic use of the Twitter hashtag. He studied Twitter hashtags from a discourse narrative perspective, focusing on 'commentary' hashtags. These are used to provide an additional meaning (usually evaluative) to the semantic content of a tweet. His research went beyond previous works by focusing on contexts rather than taking just the word-class frequency into consideration. He observed the different pragmatic functions as used by each gender. Through the identification of a correlation between such linguistic behaviour and gender, it is suggested that users tend to perform gender even on the internet, where anonymity is possible.

According to Goodwin (2015), hashtags developed over time from their primary function to being a way to provide social commentary, impart sarcasm, and other narratives on social media posts". She suggests that hashtags represent a fast means of communication that facilitates rapid connections and caters for the needs of young generations who usually have a short attention span and seek instant gratification (Goodwin, 2015).

Baghirov et al. (2016), on the other hand, studied the gender differences in Instagram hashtags and found that females use more emotional and positive hashtags, as opposed to males who seem to use more informative and negative hashtags. Based on the relevance theory, Scott (2018) also studied the use of hashtags as a new way of communication, and suggests that by labelling the topic, the experiential hashtags do not only serve the searching function, but also perform a contextualization function by supplying the semantic field that should be used to interpret a given message.

Mahfouz (2020) examined the linguistic features of the hashtag with particular focus on its use in the Arabic language. By observing Instagram posts by Egyptian and Arab participants, the study determined the morpho-syntactic features of the hashtag that were included, based on the taxonomy proposed by Caleffi (2015). Her findings indicate a number of similar and different aspects between English and Arabic hashtags.

6. CONCLUSION

The present article reviewed the hashtag as a new linguistic phenomenon observed in social media discourse. It introduced the cyberspace by describing the nature of social media platforms as well as the communication and discourse used on them. Special attention is paid to the linguistic function that the hashtag performs online, after which a comprehensive overview is presented concerning the attempts of different researchers to analyse the functionality of hashtags linguistically. The conclusion can be drawn that the hashtag has grown to be an essential feature of online discourse on social media platforms, whose functionality extends further outside the linguistic scope over time. However, no comprehensive analytic framework is presented to deal with the hashtag on more than one linguistic level. Therefore, it is recommended that future works should explore the linguistic theories that could be used in classifying the functions of hashtags online.

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